

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in Yatta

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Global Journal of Engineering and Technology Advances, 2023, 17(02), 106–119

Publication history: Received on 05 October 2023; revised on 16 November 2023; accepted on 19 November 2023

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/gjeta.2023.17.2.0234>

Abstract

The study aimed to investigate the role of educational supervisors in the development of school administration in government schools in the educational district of Yatta. To achieve this, a descriptive-analytical approach was employed, involving a personal interview with the study sample. The study population consisted of all educational supervisors working in the Directorate of Education in the city of Yatta, with a sample size of six supervisors. The following key results were obtained:

- Supervisors play a significant role in developing the administrative process in schools, by:
- The educational supervisor contributes to the introduction of new administrative methods to enhance school administration.
- The educational supervisor assists the principals in developing the technical and managerial skills necessary for the educational process and school management.
- Based on the study's findings, the following recommendations were formulated:
- The necessity of selecting educational supervisors based on criteria and standards that ensure the realization of the concept of administrative supervision, where service in school administration is one of these criteria. Additionally, there is a need to enhance the relationship between the school and the supervisor with the local environment.
- The differentiation between administrative supervisors and specialized supervisors.

Keywords: School Administration; Educational Supervisors; Yatta Directorate of Education

1. Introduction

Education is a social process and a responsibility that we are held accountable for before God Almighty. It is closely linked to society and its various circumstances worldwide. Education illuminates the path for educators and those working towards comprehensive and integrated development, especially in the era of knowledge explosion and the information revolution, necessitating continuous progress. Attaining these aspirations requires a tool for precise scientific planning and prudent guidance to advance the educational process in the face of these changes in general, and to supervise it specifically. Education is among the social systems that have responded to the features of progress and development through efforts to improve schools, design curricula, and provide resources (Hamdan, 2005, p. 3).

"Contemporary societies are measured by the achievements of their educational systems and their level of development. Thus, it is not surprising that nations resort to education as an effective remedy to address their issues and areas of deficiency. The journey of education is closely linked to the journey of society and its educational ideology. To establish positions capable of emergence and effectiveness, which focus on developing our administrative and enlightening

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concepts, and field practices, adopting methods that invest in our human and strategic resources in educational systems, relying on their development and renewal, is essential. Educational development is based on the development of its opinions and management" (Al-Aga, 2002, p. 129).

The importance of the need for a special quality of school principals emerges, so that they can deal with the aforementioned challenges and implement them according to the outlined objectives. For the school principal to carry out all of his administrative and educational duties effectively, he requires the assistance of educational supervisors from various specialties. Thus, educational supervision in all its specialties has become one of the most important factors directly contributing to the development of school administration. Educational supervision acts as the link between the field and educational policy, thus serving as the basis for evaluation and development. Therefore, it has become a necessity in the educational process to achieve the best results and educational methods (Khaled, 2006, p. 50).

One of the first concerns of educational supervision was the development of school administration and the endeavor to achieve everything that would facilitate the tasks of those working at this level of educational administration. Since the responsibility of selecting, training, and developing the performance of school administrators lies with the educational supervision departments in all its specialties and orientations, this requires more attention to these aspects by all educational supervisors (Al-Masoudi et al., 2004, p. 100).

Educational literature emphasizes the importance of the role of educational supervision in assisting the school principal in performing his administrative and educational roles. The educational supervisor has gained practical experience from his practice of teaching and supervision, making him capable of supporting the school principal with these abilities and assisting him in problem-solving (Awadallah, 2006).

1.1. Research Problem

Assisting the school principal both educationally and administratively is a process in which all educational supervisors can contribute. This stems from the necessity of integrating the roles of educational supervision entities to activate what is expected of them to develop the school's work, deal with its novelties, and meet its implementation requirements. As educational supervision and school administration are integrated tasks, the researcher sees justification in studying the role of the supervisor in supporting and developing school administration. Therefore, the research problem can be defined in the following main question: What is the role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in the Yatta Education Directorate, from the perspective of the educational supervisors themselves? From this main question, the following sub-questions arise:

- Does the educational supervisor have a role in introducing new administrative methods to develop school administration?
- Does the educational supervisor have a role in developing managerial skills for the principal?
- Does the educational supervisor have a role in developing technical skills for the principal?

Study Objectives

The research aims to identify the role of educational supervisors in the development of school administration in government schools in the Yatta Education Directorate from the perspective of the educational supervisors themselves. The study also aims to identify the following points:

- To understand the role of the educational supervisor in introducing new administrative methods to develop school administration.
- To understand the role of the educational supervisor in developing managerial skills for the principal.
- To understand the role of the educational supervisor in developing technical skills for the principal.

1.2. Study Significance

1.2.1. Theoretical Significance

The theoretical significance of the study lies in addressing the important educational concept of school administration. It is known that effective administration leads to the achievement of desired objectives in an efficient manner. Therefore, the study sheds light on the concept of educational supervision and its role in the development of school administration, ultimately serving the educational objectives of the school.

1.2.2. Practical Significance

The practical significance of the research lies in the following points:

- Highlighting the role of the educational supervisor in the development of school administration.
- The current study's results may contribute to correcting and improving the reality of school administration in the city of Yatta.
- The current study's results may assist decision-makers in the Directorate of Education in the city of Yatta in benefiting from the educational supervisor in improving school administration in the city.
- Future researchers may benefit from the results of the current study in constructing their study tools and formulating their problems.

1.2.3. Study Determinants

- Objective Determinants: The role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in the educational district of Yatta from the perspective of the educational supervisors themselves.
- Spatial Determinants: Director of Education in the city of Yatta.
- Temporal Determinants: The current study was conducted during the first semester of the academic year 2023-2024.

Human Determinants: Educational supervisors in the Directorate of Education in the city of Yatta.

1.2.4. Study Terminology

- Educational Supervision: It refers to organized, continuous, cooperative educational activities carried out by educational supervisors, school principals, peers, and teachers themselves. Its purpose is to enhance and develop the teaching skills, ultimately leading to the achievement of educational learning objectives. This constitutes a comprehensive, technical, consultative, and leadership-oriented process, aiming to evaluate and enhance the educational and pedagogical process in all its aspects (Al-Saud, 2002).

Operationally, it is defined as an organized technical process performed by leaders with diverse experiences (from various specialties) to assist those in their work positions, particularly school principals. This is done with the intention of empowering them to enhance school performance and everything that contributes to raising the level of the teaching and learning processes.

- Role: It is represented by the objectives that the supervisor must achieve by evaluating the teacher through various supervisory methods, providing feedback to the teacher, and interacting with the teacher to improve their performance. This includes strengthening strengths and minimizing weaknesses (Abdul-Rasoul, 2008, p. 24).

Operationally, it is defined as a set of behaviors and actions performed by the educational supervisor by virtue of their position to address the behaviors of teachers and principals in schools.

- School Administration: It involves influencing a group of humans (students) so that they continue to grow towards specific goals, facilitated by another group, which is the teachers (Hassan and Al-Ajmi, 2007).

1.3. The Theoretical Framework

Educational supervision encompasses all aspects of the educational learning process, constituting its domain and field. Therefore, it is considered a crucial means for enhancing the quality of education. Development is the primary goal of educational supervision, enabling education to efficiently and effectively achieve its objectives and goals. The key areas of development undertaken by educational supervision include elevating the educational proficiency of teachers, guiding them towards continuous progress, and assisting them in resolving their challenges, given that they are pivotal elements in the educational learning scenario. This is accomplished through providing them with the necessary educational expertise, disseminating and fostering the exchange of these experiences. This is achieved through organizing seminars, conducting educational workshops, undertaking research, arranging courses, and providing educational facilities to address the situation (Al-Balouri, 2011, p. 8).

1.3.1. Concept of Educational Supervision

In reality, educators have not reached a specific, agreed-upon definition for supervision. This can be attributed to the diversity and variation in philosophical perspectives, attitudes, viewpoints, and understanding of its general framework. Some consider educational supervision as a human communication process, commencing with a sender, commonly referred to as the supervisor, coordinator, or inspector, and concluding with a recipient represented by the teacher or administrator.

Educational supervision is defined as a democratic, cooperative, and organized leadership process. It encompasses all elements of the educational situation, including curriculum, methods, techniques, learning environment, and students. Its aim is to study the influencing factors in this situation, evaluate them, and work towards enhancing and organizing them to achieve the best learning and teaching objectives. It is known as an interactive process, and the supervisor is an educational leader striving to enhance the educational learning process and work on its development. Thus, it is incumbent upon the educational supervisor to consider the objectives sought by educational supervision, which enable them to understand their profession and assist them in performing it in the best possible manner (Al-Agha, 2008, p. 150).

The guide for the educational supervisor issued by the educational department of UNICEF and UNESCO defines it as a directed activity based on studying the current situation. Its purpose is to serve all those working in the field of education, to unleash their capacities, enhance their personal and professional levels, thus achieving an elevation in the educational learning process and realizing its objectives. This directed activity derives its philosophy, objectives, and methods from the prevailing societal philosophy and its objectives from the prevailing educational philosophy, as it reflects the values, norms, and standards prevailing in society (Al-Badri, 2001, p. 18).

The process of educational supervision is a highly significant operation within the educational system, especially in the processes of learning and teaching. It involves effective communication among four sensitive and fundamental parties, namely, the supervisor, teacher, principal, and student. If the relationship between the teacher and the student, as well as between the supervisor and the teacher, and the student and the principal, is close and robust, it works for the common good with mutual trust among all four parties. This results in education and learning at a level where the outcomes are cohorts of graduates who work diligently to serve the nation and its citizens (Maddanat, Barza, 2002, p. 80).

1.3.2. Stages of Educational Supervision Evolution

Educational supervision has undergone stages of development before reaching its current form, which differs significantly from the concepts prevailing in the past. The study of the history of educational supervision reveals that the concept originated from the need to expand schools and to become acquainted with teachers and their teaching methods. This led to the emergence of inspection, which is the oldest form of educational supervision. It emerged with the evolution of the roles of school principals and educational directors, who were tasked with inspection responsibilities that extended to various aspects of educational activity and outcomes.

It is notable that this type of supervision was characterized by authoritarianism and coercion, associated with enforcement and compulsion. The aim was to ensure that teachers followed the rules of education under the supervision of inspectors or school principals. The desire to improve teacher performance led some supervisors to compel teachers to follow their orders, believing that this approach would lead to the development of education and teachers.

As knowledge and educational tools advanced, inspection became an unacceptable concept. The emergence of educational leadership, participation, and freedom resulting from the progress in behavioral sciences and the advancement of psychological and educational research, led to changes in social norms and values. This, in turn, contributed to the rejection of inspection values, methods, and principles (Al-Jarjawi, Al-Nakhala, 2009, p. 9).

Subsequently, there was a shift in the philosophy of educational supervision towards focusing on establishing positive human relationships between supervisors and teachers to stimulate their motivation towards work. Teachers began to be viewed based on their needs and capabilities. Supervision aimed at improving the work and performance of teachers, assisting them in their personal development, and resolving their problems. It emphasized cooperation between educational supervisors and teachers within a framework of respect and healthy human relations (Al-Taani, 2005, p. 33).

This shift marked the beginning of modern democratic supervision, characterized by collaboration between the supervisor and the teacher. It recognized the teacher as a capable individual, capable of innovation, creativity, research,

experimentation, and investigation. The teacher was entrusted with the responsibility of guiding education, determining its policies, and solving its problems. The supervisor in this context became an advisor, guide, and collaborator with the teacher, providing assistance (Al-Jarjawi, Al-Nakhala, 2009, p. 10).

1.3.3. The stages of educational supervision in Palestine can be summarized as follows

- **Inspection Stage:** In this stage, inspection focused on identifying teachers' errors. It was carried out through surprise classroom visits. The inspector assessed the teacher's mastery of the subject matter and the students' performance. The inspector might request the teacher's lesson plan during the class, in front of the students, causing discomfort. The visit might extend beyond one class, causing disruption in the school schedule. After the visit, the supervisor met with the teacher in the principal's office to discuss the teacher's shortcomings without addressing any positive aspects. This approach led to negative attitudes among teachers towards inspectors (Al-Jarjawi, Al-Nakhala, 2009, pp. 9-10).
- **Guidance Stage:** This stage emerged as a result of educational and social studies, especially those related to theories of growth, learning, human relations, and communication methods. Supervision was viewed as a social interaction process aimed at raising the professional level of teachers to the highest possible degree. Supervisors began to establish plans and objectives before visiting schools. The role of the supervisor changed, focusing on guidance as a human, democratic, cooperative process aimed at developing the learning process, improving teacher work, and shifting from inspection to guidance. This concept of supervision was based on cooperation between the supervisor and the teacher, rejecting imposition and coercion, and respecting differences of opinion while recognizing the true value of diligence (Atoui, 2001, p. 50).
- **Educational Supervision Stage:** In this stage, the term "supervision" replaced "guidance" because supervision is more comprehensive, and guidance is a part of it. The concept of educational supervision evolved due to rapid developments in educational thought. It became a process aimed at helping teachers, guiding them, and collaborating with them to develop the education process and enhance the performance of teachers through a collaborative program based on cooperation, consultation, and innovation between teachers and supervisors (Al-Hariri, 2006, p. 15).

Educational supervision now looks comprehensively at the educational situation and aims to develop the capacities of all parties to contribute to the educational process. Within this concept, the educational supervisor becomes an educational leader, whose goal is not only to bring about a change in the educational behavior of the teacher, but to attempt to bring about a change in all elements of the educational situation.

- This means that educational supervision is a process that relies on study and investigation rather than inspection.
- It encompasses all elements of the educational process, including curriculum, methods, teacher, learner, and environment, instead of focusing solely on the teacher.
- It employs diverse means and activities instead of being limited to visits and reports.

It is based on cooperative scientific planning and evaluation rather than individual effort (Al-Akar, 2008, pp. 46-47)

A Supervision in Education aims, in general, to enhance the processes of learning and teaching by improving all influencing factors and addressing the encountered problems. This is achieved through the integration and harmonization of all elements of the educational setting to achieve the desired educational objectives. There are several objectives for educational supervision as follows:

- Monitoring the teacher's work inside the classroom and evaluating the mistakes that may occur.
- Strengthening the teacher's strengths and utilizing them by presenting them to peers for knowledge exchange.
- Providing the school's needs and filling any deficiencies in terms of staff and educational materials.
- Proposing training programs for new teachers and those in need of improving their efficiency.
- Assisting the teacher in implementing their experiences in practice and harnessing them for the benefit of the learners.
- Instilling confidence in teachers, encouraging teamwork, and supporting them in self-assessment and development of their work autonomously. (Hariri, 2006, p.16)

1.3.4. The principles underlying educational supervision

Are primarily based on a group of specialists who collaborate and interact together to achieve their goals. This collaboration, based on sound and sturdy foundations, is an essential requirement for achieving comprehensive outcomes.

Therefore, it is imperative to establish robust principles upon which educational supervision operates in order to fulfill its role in achieving the desired educational objectives in the most expeditious and cost-effective manner possible. Among the prominent principles is that educational supervision is:

- **Comprehensive:** Viewing the supervision process as one that concerns all aspects of the educational setting and all elements of the educational process, including teacher, student, curriculum, methods, environment, and school facilities, with the aim of improving and elevating their levels.
- **Democratic:** Supervision primarily relies on a democratic approach that does not allow each individual to act as they please, but rather emphasizes dynamism, understanding, and sensitivity to the role of the educational leader. It also involves the collaboration and integration of all working members through formal and informal relationships in implementing the educational program.
- **Humanitarian:** This is achieved by working to clarify the needs of individuals in the educational field, including human relationships among faculty members, based on friendship, informal interaction, mutual trust, and respect. (Al-Akhr, 2008, p.51)
- **Encouraging Creativity:** This is accomplished through creative thinking, where accessing new ideas and work is the result of deep thinking, research, and experimentation. The educational supervisor can enable teachers' creativity and innovation by allowing them the freedom to think and involving them in improving objectives, content, curriculum, teaching methods, and evaluation, while encouraging them to experiment, instilling self-confidence, recognizing their efforts, and believing in their capabilities.
- **Leadership-oriented:** It involves the ability to influence teachers, students, and others related to the educational process in the school, to coordinate their efforts for the improvement and development of this process. (Al-Akhr, 2008, p.52)
- **Technical:** It aims to improve teaching and learning through continuous nurturing, guidance, and activation of continuous growth for teachers, students, and the supervisor himself, as well as any other person who has an impact on improving the educational process.
- **Collaborative:** It emphasizes involving supervisors, directors, teachers, students, and parents in planning, implementation, and evaluation by coordinating their efforts and organizing them collectively.
- **Scientific:** It is based on research, observation, and experimentation in order to develop the educational process.
- **Flexible:** Educational supervision is considered a flexible, advanced process that has proven its flexibility by employing multiple methods and means to achieve the desired objectives. (Abdulhadi, 2002, p.30)
- **Forward-looking:** The supervisor gains the ability to anticipate problems facing the work, taking preventive measures to avoid them before they occur. The supervisor acquires this ability through life experience and scientific study of the past and present.
- **Criticism and Self-criticism:** In order to prevent the educational process from deviating from its original course, the educational supervisor accepts the principles of criticism and self-criticism. The team working with the supervisor is trained to accept it as a safety valve that prevents deviation towards undesirable goals. Criticism plays its constructive and corrective role in helping to clarify the vision and does not allow for misrepresentation of positions. (Tafesh, 2004, pp.75-76)

1.3.5. Competencies Required for Educational Supervision

An educational supervisor operates in a broad field and undertakes supervisory roles that make them an educational leader. Success is not guaranteed unless they possess the necessary competencies. Scientific competencies refer to a set of scientific skills possessed by the educational supervisor, enabling them to carry out their supervisory tasks. Competency entails the ability to perform tasks with a certain level of mastery, ensuring the achievement of desired outcomes in the behavioral performance of learners, enabling effective execution of their duties, and motivating teachers for successful collaborative work.

In order for the educational supervision apparatus to effectively carry out its assigned tasks within its modern conceptual framework, individuals holding this responsibility must be equipped with competencies that qualify them for these critical educational responsibilities. (Al-Akhr, 2008, p.53)

The competencies expected of an educational supervisor can be categorized into different types, with the most relevant for serving the purposes of educational supervision being:

- **Personal Competencies:** These encompass qualities that aid the educational supervisor in achieving their objectives smoothly. They include vitality, endurance, psychological and emotional balance, discipline, responsibility, setting a good example for teachers, high mental capabilities, a sense of humor, wit, openness to

new ideas, initiative and innovation, enabling them to make sound decisions without hesitation, and the ability to act swiftly in various situations.

- **Performance Competencies for the Educational Supervisor:** The educational supervisor must possess fundamental performance competencies distributed across the various processes of educational supervision, including daily, weekly, monthly, quarterly, and yearly levels. These include:
 - Planning to achieve educational supervision objectives at different levels.
 - Defining the content of educational supervision areas, from curriculum development concepts to improving classroom teaching.
 - Implementing various individual supervision methods, such as classroom visits and sending bulletins within dedicated supervisory campaigns.
 - Evaluating various supervision processes with feedback for all concerned parties. (Al-Akhr, 2008, p.54)
- **Scientific and Intellectual Competencies:** This refers to the educational supervisor's ability to engage in constructive thinking and purposeful questioning, improve the learning environment, consider individual differences among teachers, and be able to deal with various types of teachers effectively. It also involves using scientific methods to solve problems, assessing teachers based on their achieved results, working towards building self-supervision skills in teachers, understanding the principles and foundations on which curricula are built, knowledge of supervisory methods that enable them to perform their supervisory duties, mastery in identifying training needs for teachers, proficiency in training and development, and preparing activities to meet specific program and curriculum needs. (Abdulhadi, 2002, p.31)
- **Technical Competencies:** Technical competencies refer to specialized knowledge in scientific disciplines and the proficiency in using this knowledge effectively to achieve objectives. These competencies are acquired through experience and training. They include:
 - A. The ability to plan, analyze, and complete tasks and make decisions.
 - B. The ability to diagnose and remedy faults.
 - C. The ability to objectively evaluate teachers.
 - D. Carrying out tasks correctly based on selecting the best alternatives.
- **Human Competencies:** The educational supervisor's ability to interact with teachers, coordinate their efforts, and foster teamwork among them. This requires mutual understanding between the supervisor and teachers, knowing their opinions, preferences, and attitudes. This necessitates that the educational supervisor possesses:
 - A. The ability to establish good relationships and respect for teachers.
 - B. Providing opportunities for teachers to innovate and creating a sense of security for them.
 - C. Providing opportunities for teachers to fulfill their desires and needs.
 - D. Providing freedom and a sense of security for teachers to express their opinions and proposals.
- **Cognitive Competencies:** These pertain to the educational supervisor's ability to envision the development of the teachers they supervise and understand their relationships within the institution and the working environment. These competencies involve planning, formulating a vision, and having a future-oriented perspective on their work. This task requires intellectual and cognitive competencies, leading to positive behaviors in teachers characterized by creativity and teamwork. (Atiani, 2005, p.46).

1.3.6. Previous studies

Study (Al-Bawat, 2022) aimed to identify the role of the educational supervisor in enhancing the performance of teachers in Jordanian schools. The study addressed the concept of the educational supervisor and the tasks associated with their role, and highlighted the role of the educational supervisor in improving the teacher's performance. It emphasized that improving the performance of teachers has a direct impact on the students' level and the educational system within the school. This is achieved through enhancing the leadership capabilities of teachers, improving the teaching process, developing the quality of teaching, and providing training and qualification for teachers through the use of advanced and modern tools and methods in the educational process.

The study adopted the descriptive analytical approach, which is widely used in the study of social and human phenomena. The descriptive approach serves as a tool and method for analyzing and describing the role of the educational supervisor in enhancing the performance of teachers in Jordanian schools.

The study concluded with a set of results and recommendations. It affirmed that improving the performance of teachers positively affects the students' level and the educational system within the school. The study recommended that the Ministry of Education should review and amend its educational supervision plans and areas in order to achieve the necessary knowledge and skills for the knowledge economy.

Study (**Abu Daher, 2019**) aimed to assess the degree of the educational supervisor's practice in enhancing the creative performance of elementary school teachers in the southern provinces of Palestine and ways to develop it. The researcher employed the descriptive analytical method, with the study population consisting of all elementary school teachers in the southern provinces of Palestine, totaling 3088 teachers. The study sample comprised 400 randomly selected teachers.

The questionnaire was used as a tool for data collection, consisting of 35 items divided into four domains (educational process planning, lesson management and classroom control, teacher evaluation of student performance). The data from the questionnaire were analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The researcher concluded the following important results:

- The degree of the educational supervisor's practice in enhancing the creative performance of elementary school teachers had a relative weight of 50.31 with a moderate level of estimation.
- There were statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the means of the sample individuals' ratings for the degree of the educational supervisor's practice in enhancing creative performance, attributed to the gender variable in favor of females.
- There were statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the means of the sample individuals' ratings for the degree of the educational supervisor's practice in enhancing creative performance, attributed to years of service in favor of those with 10 or more years of experience.
- There were no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the means of the sample individuals' ratings for the degree of the educational supervisor's practice in enhancing creative performance, attributed to the academic qualification variable.

The study's most important recommendations included the activation of a supervision oversight system by the Ministry of Education and Higher Education, as well as conducting workshops with teachers to establish educational objectives.

On the other hand, study (**Al-Mawaddeh, Nasri, 2018**) aimed to assess the practice degree of educational supervisors in their roles and to determine the impact of study variables: gender, type of school, experience, and academic qualification on this degree. The researcher used the descriptive survey method, with the study population consisting of all government school principals in the first district of Zarqa, totaling 157 principals. The study sample was the same as the study population. To achieve the study's objectives, a questionnaire was designed, content validity was ensured, and reliability coefficient was calculated to be 0.96. Data analysis was conducted using the SPSS statistical analysis package. The study arrived at the following results:

The degree of the supervisors' practice in developing school administration was high, with an average score of 68.3 for the overall domain. Coordination, organization, and evaluation were rated high, while planning, guidance, and training were rated with a moderate degree.

There were no statistically significant differences in the means of the directors' opinions regarding the role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in Tareq Ibn Ziyad schools, attributed to gender, academic qualification, and type of school. However, there were statistically significant differences attributed to years of experience in the areas of guidance, coordination, training, and evaluation in favor of those with less than 5 years of experience.

The study recommended several suggestions, including the distinction between administrative and technical supervisors, and that selection of educational supervisors should consider service in school administration as one of the necessary conditions for this profession.

Finally, study (**Al-Hawamdeh, 2017**) aimed to determine the feasibility of applying Six Sigma methodology in school management in Jarash province and its role in administrative development from the perspective of school principals and educational supervisors. It also sought to investigate whether the feasibility of applying Six Sigma principles varies with different variables: job title, academic qualification, and years of experience. The study sample consisted of 118 school principals and 26 educational supervisors in the Directorate of Education in Jarash province in the first semester of the academic year 2016/2017.

The study adopted a descriptive methodology. In order to achieve the study's objectives, the researcher developed two surveys. The first survey consisted of (55) items distributed across six domains (planning, information management, beneficiary satisfaction, continuous improvement, teamwork, and quality). Its aim was to investigate the opinions of the study sample regarding the feasibility of applying Six Sigma methodology principles in school administration. The

second survey consisted of (36) items distributed across four domains (students, professional development of teachers, curriculum and textbooks, and community relations). Its aim was to investigate the opinions of the study sample regarding the role of applying Six Sigma methodology principles in administrative development of school management in the four domains. The validity and reliability of the study instruments were confirmed, and they were subsequently applied to the study sample. After conducting appropriate statistical analyses, the study results revealed the potential and capabilities of school principals and educational supervisors to apply Six Sigma methodology principles in school administration to varying degrees. It was found to be high for the principles of planning and teamwork, and moderate for the principles of quality, continuous improvement, information management, and beneficiary satisfaction. The combined instrument yielded a moderate degree. Furthermore, the results showed a difference in the possibility of applying Six Sigma methodology principles in school administration based on job title, educational qualification, and years of experience.

Based on the study results, the researcher recommends that the Ministry of Education increase the training of school principals and educational supervisors in quality management techniques in general.

The study by (Al-Sreihin 2017) aimed to identify the role of educational supervisors in achieving sustainable professional development for teachers in public schools in the Al-Ramtha district, as perceived by school principals. A purposive sample of (57) principals was selected to whom a questionnaire consisting of (36) items distributed across four domains (training and development, communication, information technology, and teamwork) was administered. The validity and reliability of the questionnaire were verified. The study findings indicated that the role of educational supervisors in the four domains of the study in achieving sustainable professional development for teachers in public schools in the Al-Ramtha district, as perceived by school principals, fell within the "average" level. There were no statistically significant differences between the means of the roles of educational supervisors in achieving sustainable professional development for teachers in public schools in the Al-Ramtha district, as perceived by school principals, attributed to years of experience, educational level, or teaching stage.

Based on the study results, the researcher recommends enhancing the concept of the supervisor, highlighting its importance and role in achieving sustainable professional development for teachers.

The study by (Mustika et al. 2022) aimed to determine the role of school principals in developing the educational competencies of elementary school teachers. This research suggests that to enhance the educational competence of teachers, academic supervision by the principal is crucial. The study employed a descriptive qualitative approach. Data collection techniques included observation, interviews, and document review. Data validity was tested using source triangulation and technical triangulation. Data analysis techniques included data collection, data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing. The study concluded that the principal acts as a supervisor in developing the educational competencies of teachers by implementing activities for reviewing learning tools, monitoring learning tools, and selecting supervision assessment tools.

(Sudarni's study 2021) described the implementation of supervision by the principal of General Public Elementary School 2 in Mwara Tilang. This research applied a qualitative approach. Data was collected through observation and interviews. The results indicated that the principal develops and socially configures supervision programs for all teachers. In doing so, teachers understand and comprehend the program. The principal then supervises the teachers as planned. The supervision led to an improvement in teacher performance.

(Mestarihi's study 2020) aimed to identify the role of educational supervisors in enhancing the professional performance of social studies teachers in Jordan from the perspective of teachers in Irbid Governorate, Jordan, by determining the impact of gender, academic qualifications, educational level, and years of experience variables during the academic year 2019/2020. The study used a descriptive and analytical methodology consisting of (120) social studies teachers (60 teachers of each gender) randomly selected from a population of (690) teachers distributed in (487) government schools. The researcher prepared a questionnaire which was used. The results showed that both genders agreed that educational supervisors play a significant role in enhancing the professional performance of social studies teachers. There was a statistically significant effect at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) attributed to the gender variable in the areas of planning and teaching methods in favor of females. Additionally, there was a statistically significant effect at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) attributed to the academic qualifications variable in the areas of planning and teaching methods in favor of higher degree holders. The results also showed that there is an effective role for the educational supervisor in enhancing the professional performance of social studies teachers from the perspective of teachers in Irbid Governorate, Jordan, in the areas of planning, relationship with colleagues, and local community in favor of elementary schools. There was no statistically significant effect for class visits and evaluations based on years of experience with varying levels.

2. Material and method

The study formulated its chapters, sections, and requirements based on the descriptive-analytical approach. This method involves analysis relying on sufficient and accurate information about a specific phenomenon or subject within known time periods. The aim is to obtain practical results that can be objectively interpreted in accordance with the actual data of the phenomenon.

2.1. Study Population

The study population consists of all educational supervisors working in the Directorate of Education in the city of Yatta, totaling (20) according to the statistics of the Directorate of Education in the city of Yatta for the year (2023).

2.2. Study Sample

The sample consisted of (6) male and female supervisors, selected using purposive sampling. Table (1) illustrates the demographic characteristics of the sample.

Table 1 Demographic sample characteristics

Variable	Variable Levels	Number	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	4	66.67
	female	2	33.33
Total Percentage		100.0	

2.3. Study Tool

Description of the Scale: To understand the role of educational supervisors in the development of school administration in government schools in Yatta, the study developed a tool in the form of interview questions, drawing from the experiences of supervisors and previous studies. The questionnaire consisted of two sections: the first section included primary data such as gender and department, while the second section contained four questions assessing the role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in Yatta.

2.4. Study Variables

- **Independent Variables:** Gender, Department.
- **Dependent Variable:** The role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in Yatta.

3. Result and discussion

3.1. First: Answering the First Study Question

3.1.1. What is the role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in Yatta?

The supervisors play a significant and effective role in developing school administration. This is evident in their assistance to principals in establishing consistent administrative procedures, devising new methods aligned with resources and educational situations, and activating the director's role in providing effective and appropriate feedback through attending educational situations and supporting them in agreeing on development areas. Collaboration is crucial for the development of the educational process and effective teaching methods.

The supervisor contributes to the development of school administration by:

- Activating learning communities among teachers and administration and coordinating between them.
- Encouraging creativity and accountability.
- Collaborating with the principal in solving some administrative problems.
- Consulting with the principal on decisions related to teacher transfers and their suitability for classes and assigned tasks.
- Assisting the principal in proper planning and executive monitoring.

- Ensuring adherence to regulations and instructions from the Ministry of Education.
- Modifying and developing school plans as needed.
- Providing advice and guidance to the school administration, both administratively and technically.
- The educational supervisor also plays a crucial role in conducting training courses to develop school administration.

3.2. Second: Answering the Second Study Question

3.2.1. Is there a role for the educational supervisor in creating new administrative methods to develop school administration? What indicates this?

The educational supervisor provides experience to the school administration to enhance their administrative competencies and skills through various actions, including describing behaviors and practices that reflect values, attitudes, and thinking patterns.

The supervisor contributes to developing school administration by creating new administrative methods through continuous improvement in the desired educational objectives. The role of the supervisor is evident in enabling the administrative skills of school principals in planning, organizing, directing, monitoring, and evaluating, especially as they relate to the learning process.

In conclusion, the educational supervisor plays an important role in creating new administrative methods to develop school administration. Indicators of this include:

- Providing suggestions.
- Directing research and innovation.
- Encouraging collaboration between administrative and educational teams.
- Evaluating the results achieved from new management methods.
- Coordinating efforts among team members.

3.3. Third: Answering the Third Study Question

3.3.1. What is the role of the educational supervisor in developing the managerial skills of the principal?

The supervisor plays a prominent role in developing managerial skills and enhancing the capabilities of the principal to bring about positive changes in the educational process. This is achieved through:

- Encouraging the principal to create incentives to enhance the efficiency of school staff.
- Urging the principal to practice a participatory leadership style.
- Encouraging the principal to prioritize roles that serve the student's interests and achievements foremost.
- Promoting the qualifications and generalization of competencies.
- Providing the necessary advice and training to the principal, evident in offering consultations, analyzing needs, exchanging knowledge, and assisting the principal in evaluating performance and identifying strengths and weaknesses.

3.4. Fourth: Answering the Fourth Study Question

3.4.1. What is the role of the educational supervisor in developing the technical skills of the principal?

The supervisor, as an educational expert, provides psychological support to both the administration and teachers through an organized and purposeful collaborative process. This is achieved through clear procedural programs that enable the principal to keep up with educational developments. The supervisor employs training skills, self-reflection, enriching educational curricula, supporting learning communities, activating program roles, and utilizing educational assessment strategies, communication skills, and interaction to enhance the educational process.

The development of technical skills is evident in several aspects of the learning process, including understanding curricula (objectives, methods, activities, and assessment methods), recognizing academic levels, distributing curricula, and developing plans. Additionally, it involves protecting the professional growth of teachers through exemplary work, such as preparing necessary courses, continuous distribution of responsibilities, establishing communication and interaction with teachers by understanding their needs, monitoring tests and assignments, preparing exhibits and

materials, and participating in various activities through analysis. Furthermore, it involves setting plans, organizing visits, and therapeutic plans.

The educational supervisor contributes to the development of technical skills for the principal by:

- Assisting the principal in performing their role as a resident supervisor in the school.
- Aiding the principal in developing accompanying activities for graduation.
- Transferring new and useful educational experiences to the principal.
- Providing newsletters and tools to help the principal in their tasks.
- Assisting in developing remedial plans for academic issues.
- Aiding in the preparation of the annual curriculum plan.
- Encouraging the principal to experiment with supervisory methods that contribute to developing school administration.
- Collaborating with the principal in applied or experimental research if necessary.
- Coordinating meetings between principals, whether at the individual level or through teams and committees.

The success of the educational process lies in its leadership and management, and the awareness of the principal in achieving all administrative and technical matters. The supervisors' attention and understanding of the nature of the role they play contribute significantly. Educational supervisors aim to assist the principal in their role as an educational supervisor, both administratively and technically. Their focus is not solely on one aspect but extends to all areas of the principal's work, whether in school facilities or the local community.

These results align with the findings of the study by Al-Mawadieh and Nasri (2018), emphasizing the role of supervisors in the development of school administration.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the crucial role of educational supervisors in enhancing school administration in Yatta's government schools. Findings underscore the supervisors' significant contribution to introducing new administrative methods and supporting principals' skills development. The study suggests stringent selection criteria for supervisors and emphasizes improving their relationship with the local environment. This research offers insights crucial for refining selection processes and strengthening supervisor-school ties, ultimately benefiting society by fostering more effective educational practices and better-equipped schools for future generations' growth and development.

Recommendations

After conducting this study, which aimed to examine the role of educational supervisors in developing school administration in government schools in Yatta the following key recommendations were formulated based on the study's results:

- The necessity of selecting the educational supervisor based on foundations and criteria that ensure the realization of the administrative supervision concept. One of these criteria should be the requirement for service in school administration, emphasizing the need to develop the relationship between the school and the supervisor with the local environment.
- Distinction between the administrative supervisor and the specialist supervisor.
- Undertaking further studies related to the topic, taking into consideration new variables.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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